

CDA NEWSLETTER

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BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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DVC Management Services, Prof Mahmud Umar Sani (front), Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (right), Deputy Director, Training, Prof Sanusi Gauya Mohammed, Deputy Director Outreach and Publication, Prof Amina Mustapha and Project Manager, Dr Yusuf Garba at the 7th ACE Impact Regional Workshop meeting held at Hotel de Azalai, Cotonou

CDA Applauded For Excellent Performance At 7th ACE Regional Workshop

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture was applauded for excellent performances in research and revenue generation having made 100% earnings as at March 2002. This was stated at the 7th Africa Centres of Excellence for Development Impact (ACE-Impact) regional workshop held in Cotonou, Benin republic from 13th – 17th June 2022. Review of the performances of each of the ACEs showed that the CDA made a breakthrough in research.

In terms of overall result achievement, CDA had attained 57% as at March 2022 (of Centre's total

allocation) being the 2nd among the Nigerian ACEs. This performance surpassed the country's (Nigeria) average which stood at 34%.

The main objective of the workshop was to provide support and sharing global best practices to Centres on project objectives with emphasis on development impact, entrepreneurship and innovation, gender initiatives, digital transformation and institutional impact activities.

This was in addition to mid-term review and discussion on relevant changes to project PDOs and DLIs.

Earlier during his welcome remarks at the opening ceremony, Professor Olusola Bandele Oyewole (AAU, Secretary-General) appreciated the resilience and swift adaptation to the changes demonstrated by the Centres occasioned by the Covid-19 pandemic towards meeting the primary objectives of providing high quality education.

He urged the Centres to work closely with their respective University managements

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towards ensuring the sustainability of the Centres beyond the ACE- Impact funding.

The Deputy Vice Chancellor, (Management Services), Professor Mahmud Umar Sani, led the CDA team that comprised the Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha and the ACE – Impact Project Manager, Dr Yusuf Garba.

The CDA-BUK and ACEPHAP Team in a group photograph with Executive Secretary, National Universities Commission (NUC) shortly after declaration of the workshop open

The Director General ICRISAT, Dr Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes (right) presenting a souvenir to Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left)

CDA Team Visits ICRISAT Headquarters in India

A delegation from the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria paid a visit to ICRISAT headquarters in Hyderabad, from 30th May to 1st June, 2022, to forge closer ties between the two organizations so as to address issues around dryland agriculture in the region and explore new avenues for collaboration.

The CDA delegation, led by the Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, met Dr Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes, Director General, ICRISAT; Dr Arvind Kumar, Deputy Director General-Research, Program Directors, Dr Victor Afarisefa, Dr Sreenath Dixit and senior ICRISAT scientists.

The CDA team visited various research facilities, including demonstration sites, to witness the success stories of ICRISAT's research and innovation activities.

ICRISAT and Nigeria are long-standing collaborators in developing research-for-development initiatives to overcome critical agricultural development challenges, such as enhancing crop productivity, diversification of drylands systems, strengthening farmer-market linkages and systems transformation for better livelihoods for smallholder farmers, including capacity building and training next

generation scientists and research scholars.

Some of the key areas identified during the visit for strengthening ICRISAT-CDA collaboration include training high-level human resources in target countries to generate knowledge and solutions to the challenges and harness new opportunities.

Others are soil-water conservation, land rejuvenation and soil health improvement; Climate resilience, weather advisories and climate smart technologies; Optimal utilization of high-end research facilities through shared approach and building capacity of scientists and research staff through exchange visits.

The meeting further deliberated on facilitating South-South collaboration between the Africa Higher Education Centres of Excellence for Development Impact (ACE-Impact)/ Partnership for skills in Applied Sciences, Engineering and Technology (PASET centres) and Asian Institutions working on ICRISAT's Research for Development areas of interest, as well as establishing an Agribusiness and Innovation Platform at CDA.

The delegation included officials from Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) of Bayero University, Kano,

CDA Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha (left) presenting African traditional dress to the Director General ICRISAT, Dr Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes

Nigeria; the Department of Agricultural Lands and Climate Support Service of the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Abuja, Nigeria (represented by its Director, Shehu Tijjani Bello); HarvestPlus, Nigeria (represented by the Nigeria Country Director, Yusuf Fouad Dollah).

The team from CDA was led by Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Director of CDA; Professor Amina Mustapha; Dr Muhammad Murtala Badamasi; Dr Amina Lawan Mustapha and Dr Mohammed Mustapha Bello. Dr Hakeem Ajeigbe, Country Representative – Nigeria and Principal Scientist, ICRISAT, led the group from Nigeria.

CDA Team at Mahindra-ICRISAT Watershed Project

DG ICRISAT Says Collaboration with CDA will Strengthen Value Chain Development, Climate Resilience

The Director-General of ICRISAT, Dr Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes, has heaped praises on the collaboration between the ICRISAT and CDA, saying that the collaboration has the potential to address the problem of food insecurity.

While addressing the gathering, Dr Hughes, DG ICRISAT said, "I am very glad to see our long-standing partnership with different institutions in Nigeria – particularly the Centre for Dryland Agriculture. Nigeria is very well placed to scale research innovations and transform the agricultural landscape in the drylands. ICRISAT reaffirms our commitment and support across the value chain to improve the livelihoods of smallholder farmers in the region".

"ICRISAT-CDA collaboration has the potential to contribute further in the area of water-soil conservation, climate resilience, value chain development, upstream research and capacity building. I am sure this visit will renew interest and collaboration and both organizations will further accelerate the pace of science-based productivity enhancements for food and nutrition to secure

drylands" said Dr Arvind Kumar, Deputy Director General-Research, ICRISAT.

Prof. J. M. Jibrin while appreciating ICRISAT's facilities and long-standing collaboration, said "CDA and ICRISAT have the same focus with the vision of CDA being a resilient and prosperous Africa. We have collaborated in several trainings, research, and development efforts in Africa as equal partners. During the 10th anniversary celebrations of CDA, ICRISAT was selected and honoured as CDA's best international partner. "I am highly impressed with the all-inclusive way ICRISAT is approaching research for development. The science here is high end but the translation of the science to people and impact-oriented programmes and activities appears to be seamless", he further added.

"This has been very insightful visit and I was very impressed with the Watershed Project we visited. I used to think that watershed planning is a soil water conservation measure. I have soon learned from this visit that it includes soil health, agro-forestry activities, agricultural production enhancing activities, livelihoods, increase of income activities and land restoration. It was quite revealing," expressed Engr. Shehu Tijjani Bello.

"Most of us as agricultural development practitioners delve into implementing climate sensitive interventions without really understanding what climate change in agricultural systems really means. ICRISAT campus has put in place models that really explain what climate change means and solutions to mitigate these challenges. There's no better way to understand this phenomenon than visiting ICRISAT campus. The 3-day learning will go a long way in adding value to how we initiate and implement climate sensitive value chains," said Prof. Yousuf Dollah.

Nigerian delegation with Dr Jacqueline d'Arros Hughes, Director General and Dr Arvind Kumar, Deputy Director General-Research, ICRISAT

CDA Director, Prof Jibrin Elected President Soil Science Society of Nigeria

The Director of Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, has been elected as the President of Soil Science Society of Nigeria.

The Soil Science Society of Nigeria (SSSN) is a registered body/organization of the International Union of Soil Science, with the mission "to advance the study of soil, promoting and fostering understanding of basic and applied Soil Science, nationally and internationally". The Society also strives to enhance the dissemination of knowledge in all the aspects of

Soil Science and shares ideas with national and international societies through conferences, symposia, lectures, seminars and journal publications.

Members of the University Community congratulated him on his election and wished him well. "We extend our congratulatory message to him and wish him well in this well deserved election". Dr Murtala Muhammad Badamasi stated that he has the capacity and wherewithal to lead SSSN to greater heights.

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Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Director, CDA
President, Soil Science Society of Nigeria (SSSN)

CDA to Partner with Songhai Farms, Porto Novo, Benin Republic

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano is set to sign a memorandum of understanding (MoU) with the Songhai Farm Porto Novo republic of Benin.

A Team from the Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Bayero University, Kano paid a visit to Songhai Farm Porto Novo, from 17th – 20th June 2022.

The visit was to discuss the possibility of establishing collaboration between the two organizations.

The founder and Director of Songhai farm, Father Godfrey Nzamujo, while welcoming the CDA Team expressed appreciation that the CDA found the Songhai farm worthy of collaboration.

Possible areas of collaboration that will be explored between the institutions are staff and student internships, joint trainings and research activities.

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Father Godfrey Nzamujo the founder of Songhai farms in Benin Republic stressing a point to the CDA Team during the visit to the Songhai farm

Father Godfrey Nzamujo explaining a concept while the Deputy Directors (Training) and Outreach and Publications listen with keen interest

The Founder / Director of Songhai Farms in a group photograph with the CDA Team during the visit. Left to right Dr Yusuf Garba (Project Manager, ACE-Impact), Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (Director, CDA), Prof. Amina Mustapha (Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications), Father Godfrey Nzamujo (Director/Founder Songhai Farms and Prof. Sanusi G. Mohammed (Deputy Director, Training)

CDA organizes workshop on Statistical Analyses in partnership with Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano organized a 6-day Regional Training Workshop on Data collection and Statistical analyses using the R-package for the academic staff, researchers and partners of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi (UDDM).

The training which was targeted at staff, students and partners of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi (UDDM) was from Monday 21st March – Saturday 26th March, 2022 held at the Conference Hall of the Faculty of Agronomy and Environmental Sciences, UDDM.

The training objective was to strengthen the capacity of the participants in statistical analyses to further increase their abilities, skills and knowledge while improving the quality of output and efficient performance.

The Deputy Vice Chancellor of the UDDM, Dr Adamou Saidou, who represented the Vice Chancellor during the opening ceremony expressed appreciation to the CDA and by extension Bayero University, Kano for the bond of brotherhood, which the Centre has been displaying since its existence.

He urged the participants to utilize the rare opportunity towards ensuring that they make maximum use of the training towards better capacitating their skills and knowledge in statistical analyses.

The Acting Dean of the Faculty of Agronomy and Environmental Sciences of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi, Dr ELH GOUNGA Mahamadou, in his remark applauded the strong ties between the CDA-BUK and UDDM since the establishment of the former; stressing that the CDA was one of the strong partners of the University. He thanked the Centre for the laudable efforts at strengthening the capacity of its

Group photograph of the participants of the workshop

staff, students and partners.

In his remark, the Deputy Director (Training) of the CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, stated that over the years the UDDM had proved to be a dependable partner of the Centre urging the University management to continue to support the faculty in its collaborations with the CDA.

A total of thirty-six participants comprising thirty-three (33) males and three (3) females participated in

the training. Participants displayed high enthusiasm and zeal during the training sessions and expressed delight in participating in the training.

The CDA delegation for the training was led by Professor Sanusi Gaya, the Deputy Director Training. Others were: Dr Kabir Mustapha Umar (Deputy Director, Research), Dr Yusuf Garba (Project Manager, ACE-Impact) and Dr Aminu A. Fagge (Welfare Officer).

CDA Team and participants of the workshop at Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University, Maradi

CDA's FRESH FROM THE FARM

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO

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